

Developing Coping Mechanisms for Stress Management of Researchers

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Track 1: Scientific and practitioners' research presentations

- a. Bottom-up and community-driven interventions
- b. Institutional interventions and policies
- c. Policy-Level insights

Stress is defined as an introverted reaction of individuals to situations that they perceive as a challenge or threat, or as a situation that is sometimes exposed as a result of time pressure, sometimes as a result of an unexpected event or reaction (Durna, 2006). It generally includes the psychological reactions to those threats or challenges that have an impact on well-being or physical conditions (Lazarus, 1996; 2006). Research demonstrated that Ph.D. students, especially the students in the thesis period, are in the risk groups in terms of high stress and mental health problems (Ali & Kohun, 2006; Evans, Bira, & Vanderford, 2019; Levecque et al., 2017; Mantai & Dowling, 2015; Waight. and Giardonobe, 2018). Doctoral education has a long-term nature that requires constant effort and dedication. Progress can be somewhat slow and challenging emotionally as well as cognitively (Mantai & Dowling, 2015). Recent research on the mental health of doctoral candidates shows that high-stress levels can be caused or exacerbated by characteristics of the doctoral training environment and organizational functioning (Mackie and Bates, 2019).

Ph.D. study and semester, including frequent evaluations, low status, overwork, work-life imbalance, peer pressure, deadlines, financial difficulties, career uncertainty, an academic environment partially and/or fully competitive, publication pressure, and conferences characterized by active participation in the scientific environment (Kurtz-Costes, Andrews Helmke, & Ülkü-Steiner, 2006; Mays & Smith, 2009; Schmidt & Hansson, 2018). There are additional stressors such as feelings of uncertainty and bad relationships with supervisors, and the myriad roles that the doctoral student is expected to take as a student, employee, researcher, spouse, or parent (Martinez, Ordu, Sala, & McFarlane, 2013; Schmidt & Hansson, 2018; Schmidt & Umans, 2014).). In light of the number of potential stressors and complex work situations of doctoral students, maintaining a healthy work-life balance can be

challenging, and any or more of these problems can lead to stress symptoms (Devos et al., 2017; Martinez et al., 2013).

Studies on the mental health of doctoral students conducted in different countries show that doctoral students encounter mental health problems at a much higher rate than the general population (Evans, Bira, & Vanderford, 2019; Levecque et al., 2017; Smith & Brook, 2015; Panger, 2014). Bazrafkan et al. (2016) stated that Ph.D. students mostly use effective communication to deal with stress. However, they do not have wide range of coping strategies to deal with the stress. Somatic Experiencing (SE) is an approach that addresses the problems of stress, negative life experiences and trauma while focusing on the body and its reactions (Levine, 1997; 2010). This approach helps to understand the sensations in the body and to build the innate balancing capacity of the nervous system (Levine & Frederick, 1997; Porges, 2017). Furthermore, SE is an effective approach in emergency situations to build coping mechanisms in a short time. Thus, this study aims to develop a SE-based stress-management intervention program for Ph.D. students.

Purpose

Studies demonstrated that online support groups empower the clients (Barak et al., 2008; van Uden-Kraan et al., 2009). In addition, Mariano et al. (2019) indicated that the online group processes is an effective way to create coping strategies. SE is a resiliency-based approach that uses the nervous system for regulation and demonstrates short-term results (Payne et al., 2015; Winblad et al., 2018). Briggs (2018) and Taylor and Saint Laurent (2017) expressed the effectiveness of the SE-based approach in group psychotherapy. This study aims to develop coping strategies and improve the already existed ones to reduce the stress level of PhD. students with SE-based exercises and activities in an eight-week group process. The main hypothesis of this study is as follows: Results of the scales on COPE Revised and MAIA would show a statistically significant difference in pretest and posttest compared to the control group. Furthermore, qualitative data would be expected to support the difference in quantitative data.

Design

Quasi-experimental design over a period of three months will be conducted to assess the effects of short-term group psychotherapy process. The recruitment of the group process has

not started yet. The flyer of the group psychotherapy will be announced in social media and mail groups. The control group will be formed by using the waitlist. Thus, these potential group members will be planned a short term intervention process after the quasi-experimental study.

Table 1

Study design

Weeks	0		8
Intervention Group	Pre-test	X1*	Post-test
Control Group	Pre-test		Post-test

X1= 8 sessions will be provided for the intervention group during the eight weeks.

Before starting the process, semi-structured interviews will be conducted with each potential group member for screening purposes. Group members will be decided according to the group purpose, their demographic information (age, education level, job, etc.), situations about getting psychological help from a professional, their resources while coping with stress, and scaling questions about their stress level. The related questionnaires will be sent to group members before and after the short-term intervention. Three months after the end of the process, semi-structured interviews will be conducted with participants for follow-up purposes.

Instruments

Semi-structured Interview Protocol. The semi-structured interview protocol will be developed to understand the participants' current stress levels, resources (family, friends, etc.), and health/demographic information (getting psychological help, age, employment status, education level) before the group began. Two separate interview protocols were developed by the researchers because the first protocol included questions more about the demographic data and the resources of the individual, where the second semi-structured interview protocol included questions about the group process and the interventions (i.e. Which part(s) of the group process was more helpful for you? Which techniques you are using or planning to use

in your daily life? Are there any suggestions for future group work?). These interview protocols will be revised by academic and SE practitioners.

COPE Revised. The COPE Revised (COPE- R; Zuckerman & Gagne, 2003) is a 32-item questionnaire used to screen for coping mechanisms. It contains five scales: self-help, approach, accommodation, avoidance, and self-punishment. Individuals rate each question on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (*never do this*) to 4 (*always do it*). Internal consistency of the Turkish adaptation of the scales ranges from .92 to .93 (Dicle & Ersanlı, 2015).

Multidimensional Assessment of Interoceptive Awareness -2. (MAIA 2; Mehling, Acree, Stewart, Silas & Jones, 2018). This 37-item questionnaire is developed for understanding the perception of internal bodily changes. It has eight subscales; noticing, not-distracting, not-worrying, attention regulation, emotional awareness, self-regulation, body listening, and trusting. The questionnaire is a 6-point Likert scale with zero being “never” and five being “always”. The Turkish version of the item consists of 32 items and six subscales; not-worrying, not-distracting, attention regulation, emotional awareness, self-regulation, body listening, and trusting. The internal consistency of the Turkish adaptation of the scales ranges from 1.33 to .75 (Özpinar, Dündar, Demir & Akyol, 2021).

Data Analysis

Data analysis will be conducted in two parts, including quantitative and qualitative data analysis. Quantitative analysis will be conducted by using SPSS. ANOVA (repeated measures) will be performed to assess the changes in group members and the waitlist control group. In addition, ANCOVA will be conducted to compare the effect of the dependent variable between group members. Qualitative data gathered from the semi-structured interviews will be analyzed using content analysis.

Implications

The result of the present study can be used to develop wide-range interventions for Ph.D. students by institutions and mental health services at the universities. The stressors experienced by Ph.D. students are various. Thus, these stressors should be considered by supervisors and policymakers. Since the Ph.D. students work mostly alone with their research (Tikkanen et al., 2021), particular attention should be given to creating support networks for

this vulnerable group. In addition, the importance of the intervention group will be highlighted for policymakers in this study. The results of this study will provide directions for future research.

Resources

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